

Autonomous Drone Measurement approach for Flying Base Stations

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Abstract

The widespread use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) has been the key in expanding the application domain for antenna and field measurements. This paper proposes an original system for the measurement of the transmission patterns of flying basestations, using two drones. While one drone acts as a fixed radiation source with a transmitting antenna, the other conducts a survey over predefined trajectories to capture the received signal strength. The results from various flight plans—circular, cylindrical, and spherical—revealed consistent signal strength variations with max fluctuations of approximately 2.5 dB along the vertical axis, and the spherical flight providing comprehensive spatial coverage, all peaking towards the horizontal mounting pole of the transmit antenna. This work can serve as the basis for developing efficient UAV based measurement methods that will facilitate flying ad-hoc deployment and optimization of communication networks.

Measurement setup

- Two Drones Haemus Hexacopter Skylle 1550
- Tx drone:** flying BS with Arduino microcontroller, 433 MHz 10mW CW transmitter, antenna gain 2 dBi on a horizontal mounting pole. Drone hovering at an altitude of 50 meters above ground level
- Rx drone:** with Raspberry Pi 4 SBC, Mini Digital USB 2.0 SDR, 433 MHz, 2 dBi antenna. Measures signal power every 0.1 seconds @10m from the Tx. Includes TOPGNSS USB GPS sensor for precise location data.
- Ground stations for Tx and Rx monitored and controlled the experimental process. Mission Planner for planning, configuring, simulating, and monitoring autonomous missions. Real-time data reception through telemetry systems, ensuring robust communication and data integrity.

	Mean Error (m)	Std (m)	Max Error (m)
X-Y Plane	0.09	0.07	0.36
Z Axis	0	0.09	0.15
Combined	0.11	0.09	0.49

Flight path Results

Circular flight plan: Actual trajectory of the measuring drone, with color-coded signal strength measurements.

Cylindrical flight plan: (a) Actual flight trajectory of the measuring drone with color-coded signal strength measurements. (b) Interpolated 3D cylindrical surface.

Spherical flight plan: (a) Actual flight trajectory of the measuring drone with color-coded signal strength measurements. (b) Interpolated 3D spherical surface.

Sensor Measurements

- Data collection utilized a Raspberry Pi 4 Model 4GB as a companion computer mounted on the drone
- Enviro+ HAT (Hardware Attached on Top) add-on designed for environmental measurement, connected directly to the Raspberry Pi for data acquisition
- Data transmission via the drone's telemetry system.

Sensor	Source	Data
Altimeter	Drone	Altitude
Battery	Drone	Battery Level
Raspberry Pi	Raspberry Pi	CPU Temperature
BME280	Enviro+ HAT	Temperature, Pressure, Humidity
LTR-559	Enviro+ HAT	Light
MICS6814 + ADS1015	Enviro+ HAT	Oxidised (OX sensor), Reduced (RED sensor), NH3
PM55003	Enviro+ HAT	Particulate Matter (PM1, PM2.5, PM10)

Telemetry Dashboard

Conclusions

This study evaluated the accuracy of a drone-based system for mapping flying base station transmissions. Results confirmed precise navigation and consistent signal strength variations across flight plans. The spherical flight plan provided peak signals aligning to the horizontal mounting pole. 3D mapping revealed symmetrical signal patterns influenced by drone materials, consistent with existing research. These findings highlight drones' potential for wireless system analysis and antenna validation in real-world conditions. The measurements presented in this paper can be made available upon request at wmclab@uop.gr (terms and conditions apply).

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